

Research Article

G-D’s Physics Novel Conception of the Four Basic Physical Features: Maimonides’ & Chassidic “Four Elements”!

Jehonathan Bentovish

Zefat Academic Colloge, Zefat, Israel

Corresponding author

Jehonathan Bentovish (Bentwich), Zefat Academic Colloge, Zefat, Israel

Received: 06 Aug 2023

Accepted: 10 Aug 2023

Published: 20 Aug 2023

Copyright

© 2023 Jehonathan Bentovish

OPEN ACCESS

Note: *Dr. Bentovish is calling Astronomers & Cosmologists (worldwide) to carry out a further direct empirical validation of the (already validated) New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm based on a “time-sensitive” measurement of a predicted increase in the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion – specifically during the upcoming Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH, New Year) two days’ time-interval due at: September 16th -17th 2023 (and onwards), relative to before the 16th-17th of September! Dr. Bentovish is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in this further direct validation of the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics. Dr. Bentovish’s e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com.*

Abstract

Twenty-first Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a Paradigmatic-Shift from the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) New Scientific Paradigm! This Paradigmatic Shift follows a “Paradigmatic-Crisis” of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm signified by the appearance of a basic “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM, and its principle inability to account for the accelerated expansion of the physical universe (e.g., assumed to be “caused” by purely hypothetical “dark-matter” concept comprising up to 95% of all the mass in the universe, but which could not be detected experimentally despite numerous attempts to do so!?) In contrast, the New “G-D’s Physics” is shown capable of resolving this apparent “GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency”, discards “dark-matter” as superfluous (i.e., “non-existent”) based on the discovery of a singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ (thereby producing an extremely rapid series of “Universal Frames”). Indeed, this New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm has been shown capable of not only unifying between GRT & QM through a novel “Universal Computational Formula” (UCF), but also unify between the four basic physical features of “space” and “energy”, and “mass” and “time” based on the UCP’s two basic “Computational Dimensions” (e.g., “Framework” and “Consistency”) four possible combinations – which are surprisingly found to correspond to Maimonides’ (and Chassidic Thought) Four Elements! This new profound understanding of the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP originates, sustains and evolves the entire physical universe based on these Four Elements (e.g., computation of these four basic Physical Features) also points at the UCP’s “steering” of the universe, Science and Humanity toward its “Ultimate Perfected Geulah State” in which the singularity of this UCP will be recognized (alongside its profound characteristics of “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and Harmony”, which will therefore also typify Humanity’s Perfected Geulah State)!

Introduction

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics has reached a state of a “Paradigmatic-Crisis” in which the two basic “pillars” of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm, e.g., General Relativity Theory (GRT) & Quantum Mechanics (QM) seem “theoretically inconsistent”, and in which this Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm cannot explain the accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion rate, e.g., assumed to be “caused” by purely hypothetical “dark-matter” and “dark-energy” concepts which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe, but which cannot be detected experimentally, despite twenty years of intensive experimental efforts to do so! Fortunately, a New “G-D’s Physics” (“Computational Unified Field Theory”, CUFT) has been discovered, which was shown capable of resolving this apparent theoretical inconsistency, and also offers an alternative (satisfactory) explanation for the universe’s accelerated expansion rate [1-47].

The most significant discovery made by “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) New Scientific Paradigm is the existence of a singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ thereby producing an extremely rapid series of

“Universal Frames” (UF’s) comprising the entire physical universe (at every “minimal time-point”), and that “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s the whole universe (and all of its constituent exhaustive spatial pixels) “dissolve” back into the singularity of this UCP! Indeed, the discovery that this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising each consecutive UF’s frame/s, and the complete “dissolution” of the whole universe back into the UCP’s singularity “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frames) identified this New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm as an “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm – negating the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels, e.g., existing either in the same- or different- UF’s frame/s!

Hence, our basic conception of the origin- sustenance- and development- of entire physical universe (as well as of any physical subsystem or any other physical object comprising it) changes entirely: no longer can we attribute the creation of the physical universe (as a whole), or even of any physical phenomenon or object to any direct (or even indirect) physical interactions between any relativistic (certain “massive objects” and “space-time”) or any subatomic quantum (“probe element” and corresponding “target element’s probability wave function”) – but is rather solely based on

the simultaneous computation of this singular higher-ordered Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle (UCP) of all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features, e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"! Indeed, the prerogative of the current (special) scientific article is to delineate the manner in which this UCP's simultaneous computation of these four basic physical features – as unified through its (newly discovered) "Universal Computational Formula", which completely unifies these four basic physical features, in a manner akin to Maimonides' Four Basic Elements! Maimonides' Four Basic Elements' conception depicts all physical phenomenon (or objects, as well as all "non-material spiritual elements") as being "comprised" of those "Four (basic) Elements" of "Earth", "Water", "Air" and "Fire"! The (amazing) discovery made by the New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st century Theoretical Physics is that those "Four Elements" (of Maimonides) are equivalent to "G-d's Physics" Universal Computational Formula's (UCF) depiction of the UCP's simultaneous computation of the Four basic Physical Features of "mass", "time", "space" and "energy"?!?

Indeed, as previously shown, this Universal Computational Formula (UCF) is based upon "G-D's Physics" novel conception of the manner in which this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) simultaneously computes those four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") for every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe: as derived from the UCP's computation based on the four possible combinations of the UCP's two Computational Dimensions: "Framework" ("frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent")! According to "G-D's Physics" (new) computation of these four basic physical features the UCP's computation of "Frame" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" yield the two physical features of "space" and "energy", whereas the UCP's of "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" produce the "mass" or "time" values for each exhaustive spatial pixel! One of the intriguing (and "marvelous") features of this novel UCF is the fact that it completely integrates those four basic physical features (for each exhaustive spatial pixel) – so that for instance, the UCP's computation of a given object's (pixel's) "energy" value (which represents the UCP's computation of its "Frame-inconsistent" value) is also compatible with its "mass" value (representing its "Object-consistent" computation)! This is where the great "beauty", "elegance", and "significance" of this (new) "Universal Computational Formula" is revealed, because it represents the first time (in Physics) in which those four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" are completely integrated – i.e., as "secondary-computational" by-products of this singular higher-ordered UCP's (simultaneous) computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (at the unfathomable rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec)!). Moreover (as shown previously), this UCF also completely integrates between GRT & QM – which become "special-cases" within "G-D's Physics" more exhaustive UCF's conceptualization (as can be glanced from this UCF's two respective "Relativistic" and "Quantum" Formats)!

Intriguingly, over and beyond "G-D's Physics" UCF's capacity to completely integrate between those four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") and between GRT & QM (as "special-cases" within the UCP's more exhaustive computation of the UCF), it has been shown that this new "G-D's Physics" UCF conceptualization also fully integrates between the Four (fundamental) Forces (e.g., once again for the first time in Theoretical Physics)!

The manner in which this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is able to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM is based on its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which is postulated to simultaneously compute all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, e.g., including their four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – at an unfathomably rapid rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec)! This produces an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at every such "minimal time point",

e.g., with all such exhaustive spatial pixels "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames! Additionally, as part of the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s, it also computes "Single Spatial-Temporal" (SST) relativistic "object" or subatomic "particle" computation, as well as "Multi Spatial-Temporal" (MST) computation of more than one spatial-temporal "object"/"particle" point at any given UF's frame/s, e.g., giving rise to the (relativistic or subatomic) "wave" phenomenon! Thus, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm's theoretical framework is capable of explicating the embedding of any SSP "particle", e.g., including two "entangled particles" as integral parts of the broader "MST" "wave" phenomenon – which are both embedded within the "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" (EST) UCP's computation of the entire UF's frame/s (e.g., for each consecutive UF's frame)! Viewed from this novel higher-ordered perspective of the UCP's EST computation of all exhaustive spatial temporal pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) – as embedding within it both the SST "entangled particles" and the broader MST "wave" computation allows for this New "G-D's Physics" to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM – while pointing at the much more exhaustive theoretical framework of the UCP's production of the series of UF's frame/s!

Indeed, a major discovery made by this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is the complete unification – not only between GRT & QM, but also between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (as well as between the four basic Forces!) within a newly discovered "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), which explicates the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s)! This major UCF discovery stems from "G-D's Physics" novel computation of these four basic physical features as underlie by the UCP's two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" and "Consistency": According to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm the UCP computes for each given (relativistic or subatomic) object – its degree of "Consistency" (e.g., "consistent" or "inconsistent") relative to two possible "Framework" levels, i.e., relative to the entire "frame" or relative to the "object" itself (i.e., internal composition), which gives rise to those four basic physical features; That is, when the UCP computes "Framework" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" measures of any given object this yields the two corresponding physical features of "space" and "energy", whereas when the UCP computes the two "Object" – "consistent" vs. "inconsistent" measures this produces the two corresponding physical features of "mass" and "time"! Based on these new (and exciting) UCP's computational definitions of these four basic physical features (given below) the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm was able to integrate them as secondary computational features of the same singular higher-ordered UCP, thereby giving rise to this profound novel "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF)!

THE "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF):

$$\left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} \text{UF's } \{n \dots n \dots x\} [Px]_{[a..z]} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

Note: which is accompanied by "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) computational (previous) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and

"energy", "mass" and "time" as representing "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") computational properties of the UCP's simultaneous and integrated computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels:

$$S: (f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] + \dots f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) \leq f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} \{UF's(i..n)\}$$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i..n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure!

Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the UCP:

$$E: (f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) > f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} \{UF's(i..n)\}$$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

$$M: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] = O(i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i..n)\} / h * n \{UF's(i..n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i..n) \leq n * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] \neq O(i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i..n)\} / c * n \{UF's(i..n)\}$$

such that:

$$T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i..n) \leq c * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Significantly, it has been previously shown that this novel UCF possesses two equivalent "Relativistic Format" and "Quantum Format" which indicate that it embeds (within it) "special-cases" of well-known physical laws and characteristics of GRT such as the "Energy-Mass Equivalence" ("E = Mc²") and QM's "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" "complimentary pairs"; thereby pointing at "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's complete unification- embedding- and indeed transcending- of GRT & QM! However, since one of the key Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe including all of these exhaustive spatial pixels – "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames; therefore, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm has been characterized as an "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! This is because due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and its complete "dissolution" "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames (e.g., back into the UCP's singular existence), there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s!

In fact, due to the only "transient" and "phenomenal" existence of any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, e.g., which exists only "during" the UCP's production of every consecutive UF's frame/s, but "ceases to exist" and "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two subsequent UF's frames, two additional profound Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm, termed: the "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" postulate: a) That the only "computationally-invariant" principle in the universe which exists both "during" the UCP's successive computation of each subsequent UF's frame/s, and solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) is this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP); as opposed to the only "transient-phenomenal" appearance of the entire physical universe – regarded as "computationally-variant", e.g., existing only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely computed or produced by this singular UCP) but "dissolving" back into the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; b) Therefore, there only exists one singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists uniformly, continuously and constantly – both "during" its manifestation as the physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), and also exists singularly "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe)!

Viewed from this new (higher, more exhaustive) perspective of this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, a series of additional (profound) associated Theoretical Postulates have been discovered, including: a) The "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Postulate: hypothesizing that since there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s, the only manner in which this series of UF's frames (comprising

the entire physical universe) could "evolve" is based on this singular higher-ordered UCP's "pre-planning" of the entire evolution- (or manifestation-) of the whole universe from "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards", i.e., based on the UCP's "pre-planning" of the whole evolution of all "inanimate" and "animate" forms leading up to this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! A Metaphor regarding "King Solomon's" build-up of the Divine Temple was utilized to explain this "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Postulate: that is, in the same way that King Solomon must have received a completed "Perfected Blue-Print Plan" of the "Ultimate Completed Temple State" (e.g., and all of the necessary "steps" required to reach this "Ultimate Completed Temple State" – prior to his various builders starting to construct this immaculate Divine Temple, so it is postulated that the UCP/UCR must have "pre-planned" the whole evolution of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter", "animate": plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" – through the entire evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, ultimately leading to that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State", i.e., in which Science and the whole of Humanity will recognize the singular existence of this higher-ordered UCR, alongside the recognition of its basic characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" etc. (previously delineated).

A Brief Summary of "G-D's Physics" additional Theoretical Postulates is outlined (in order to provide an exhaustive summary of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm):

b) The UCP's Three Computational Dimensions:

Indeed, the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm offers a new (and exciting) theoretical explanation for the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on two out of its three hypothesized "Computational Dimensions", e.g., "Framework" ("frame" vs. "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" vs. "inconsistent"); According to "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, the UCP simultaneously computes for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe these four basic physical features based on particular computational combinations, e.g., an "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computation derives the two (corresponding) physical features of "mass" and "time", whereas the UCP's computation of any given object's "Frame" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" values yields its "space" and "energy" characteristics!

c) The Universal Consciousness Reality's (UCR) "Ten-Hierarchical Computational Dimensions":

1) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה"):

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution" re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe – which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!?), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's"

sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

2) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of "All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah" State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality!? Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

3) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת):

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic, "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past"- "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blue-Print", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the neces-

sary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת) signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חסד"/Chessed):

this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/חסד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah" may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Gevurah"/גבורה):

denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice

that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" on order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("תפארת"/Tiferet):

the sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human -being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th, 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of

the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תפארת/Tiferet" which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification- or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("ניצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal"):

signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol of "חגיגה" "Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva" (תשובה)/"דוה"/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva" / "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("ניצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person chooses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("ניצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד"/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("יסוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "יסוד"/"Yesod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this "יסוד"/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below:)

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"תלמות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "יסוד"/"Yesod"- "Foundation" Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "כתר" / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "כתר"/"Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "כתר"/"Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational!

Figure 1. THE TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS' UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (THD-UCF):

FIGURE 2. The "UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

Indeed, the intriguing (and beautiful) discovery made (in this article) is that "G-D's Physics" new conceptualization of these four physical features corresponds to Maimonides' (and Chassidic Thought) conception of the Four Elements believed to comprise any "material" (or indeed even "spiritual") entity in the universe! *Moreover, intriguingly, we can see through "G-D's Physics" new UCP's complete integration between those four basic physical features, GRT & QM and the Four (fundamental) Forces – that in fact, Maimonides' (and Chassidic Thought) discovery reveals (to us) a new (fascinating) "facet" in "G-D's Physics" new understanding of the UCP's origination- sustenance- ("dissolution"-) re-computation- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entirety of the physical universe) towards its Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"!

Method & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-d's Physics" identified a unique "Critical-Prediction" stemming from its new "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on the UCP's singular higher-ordered two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency" (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP's Computational Dimensions definition of the "mass" of any given particle as an "object-consistent" computational measure:

$$M: \sum \{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: \{O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i) - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i\dots n)\} \leq n * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by [55,57].

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction [55,57], set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum \{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force" [50]), interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction, [54,58], higher dimension gravity, [49], a new boson, [53], and the quasi-free hypothesis $\pi+$ [52], and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashanah" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts' ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020)?! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or

indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Hence, to the extent that these two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm are empirically validated, then this will convince the Scientific Community that the New "G-D's Physics" has to be accepted as a satisfactory New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics! Based on such direct empirical validation of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, a discussion ensues of the manner in which "G-D's Physics" newly discovered singular higher-ordered Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) is capable of computing every exhaustive spatial pixel or "object" (e.g., including "human-beings" as opposed to "non-human": "inanimate" material object/s, as well as "animate": plants and animals) – based on a further discovery of the UCP's "Gimateria" (i.e., Hebrew letters' numerical values) of each object's five "secondary-essential" "Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (HCD's) of: "Chessed", "Gevurah", "Tiferet", "Neztach" & "Hod" (e.g., each of them comprising "ten zero's" out of the "fifty zero's" comprising the incredible rate of the UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe: $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec)! As will be discussed, this entirely new conception of the manner in which this singular, higher-ordered UCP computes every exhaustive spatial pixel's "object" in the universe is "non-material", i.e., exemplifying the "translation" of the fundamental new "building-blocks" ("or "Atoms" – metaphorically) of the entire physical universe from the Hebrew letters' "Gimatria" (numerical values, also associated with these five "secondary-essential" HCD's corresponding "ten zero's") to the production of each ("human" or "non-human") object's unique physical characteristics! Indeed, it is shown that this novel manner in which the UCP is seen to compute the specific physical characteristics of each individual (unique "human" or "non-human") "object" is a part and parcel of the UCP's overall "Blueprint Plan" of steering the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate" material composition through its "animate": "plants", "animals", human-beings – leading to the fulfillment of the UCP's "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of a "Moral", "Spiritual" and even "Physical" "Perfected" state of the universe in which the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), e.g., characterized by "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" being recognized (and accepted) by Science and Humanity (more generally)!

Discussion

Maimonides' & Chassidic Thought UCP's "Four Elements" Hierarchical Expansive Spectrum (HES)!

This new discovery of "G-D's Physics" basic understanding of the physical universe reveals that (in fact) the UCP's (simultaneous) computation of

these Four Physical Features – which corresponds to Maimonides' Four Elements points at the UCP's "Hierarchical Expansive Spectrum" (HES) (e.g., for every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe)! This is because when we look at the manner in which this UCP computes (for instance) the two "Object"- "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") physical features, which correspond to Maimonides' (and Chassidic Thought's) "Earth" and "Water" Elements – as opposed to the UCP's computation of the two other "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") and "inconsistent" ("energy") physical features, corresponding to Maimonides' two other "Air" & "Fire" Elements; we can see that the UCP's computation of the two "Object"- "consistent" ("mass"/"Earth") or "inconsistent" ("time"/"Water") physical features stems (or represents) a relatively more "constrictive" computation of that Object's internal composition – e.g., in terms of its "consistent" or "inconsistent" aspects "Frame, as opposed to the UCP's computation of the "Frame" – "consistent" ("space"/"Air") or "inconsistent" ("energy"/"Fire"), which refer to a relatively "more expansive" UCP computation of the degree of "consistency" or "inconsistency" relative to the entire Universal Frame/s (e.g., "coordinate-system")!

Thus, through the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New 21st Century Physics Paradigm – as being more valid than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM we in fact discover a profound new understanding and appreciation of "Maimonides & Chassidic Thought" deep understanding of the manner in which this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – i.e., steering the whole universe, and Humanity specifically towards this UCP's pre-planned "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! This is because according to the new profound scientific understanding of this UCP of the origins-sustenance- development- and "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of the universe, the universe does not exist as an "independent continuous" "material-physical" reality, but is rather being continuously computed (e.g., at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec)! simultaneously for every exhaustive spatial pixel – pertaining to its four basic physical features (of "mass" and "time", "space" and "energy") by this singular higher-ordered UCP! We also realize that since there cannot (truly) exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frames), therefore we cannot explain the origin- or the sustenance- or development- of any such exhaustive spatial pixel/s (or indeed of the entire physical universe) based on the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of GRT & QM!

Instead, we begin realizing that the only manner in which the universe can exist (e.g., and is continuously being evolved towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State") is solely based upon the singular UCP's Pre-planned "Blueprint" plan to steer and evolve the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State", in which the whole of Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this UCP and its profound characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"! Therefore, instead of the basic Old "Material-Causal" assumption which assumes that the origin and development of the entire physical universe is "caused" by direct (or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive objects" and "Space-Time" which "causes" the "curvature of Space-Time" (and conversely that it is this "curved Space-Time" which "causes" the travelling pathways of these "massive-objects" or of other "less-massive objects"), or that it is the direct "material-causal" physical interactions between a given subatomic "probe" and corresponding subatomic (assumed) "target's probability wave-function" which is assumed to "cause" the "collapse" of this "target's probability wave-function" into a singular (complimentary) "space-energy" or "mass-time" value of this target entity; the New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) negates the very possibility of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm due to the simultaneity of

the UCP's computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, and the current direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two unique "Critical Predictions"!

The intriguing and (indeed fascinating) discovery made in this article is that this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is that the manner in which "G-D's Physics" newly discovered UCP continuously computes-sustains- "dissolves"- and evolves every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, and in fact the entire physical universe is directed towards Its Preplanned "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" (e.g., from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards Humanity's and Science's realization of the singularity of this "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" and its profound intrinsic characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" typifying this Perfected Geulah State!); is based on Maimonides' (and Chassidic Thought) eluded deeper understanding of the manner in which this singular higher-ordered Reality (i.e., "G-D"!) originates and evolves the physical universe (as well as every exhaustive object or pixel comprising it)! This is because just as Maimonides discovered that every object is being "comprised" from these Four basic "Elements": of "Earth" (e.g., "mass"), "Water" (e.g., "time"), "Air" ("space") and "Fire" ("energy") – the New "G-D's Physics" (further) elucidates this profound new understanding wherein the singular higher-ordered UCP "simultaneously" computes these four basic physical features - but in fact, "successively" computes them as increasingly "more expansive" UCP's computation of the two "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") for each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, e.g., through the UCP's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"; and then successively computes the "more expansive" UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), as clearly portrayed by the UCP's THCD's Illustration!

In other words, since the manner in which the UCP has "pre-planned" the whole origination- and development of the entire physical universe, i.e., from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards that Ultimate Perfected Geulah State, is based on the UCP's Three Initial Key Hierarchical Computational Dimensions of "Wisdom", "Computation" and "Consistency" (e.g., as delineated previously) – amongst which the "Consistency" (continuous) computation of the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" for every individual human-being: wherein the free ("moral"/"immoral") choice that every such individual human-being makes (at any given moment in time) "triggers" the UCP's selection of "one of multiple possible futures" (e.g., from its "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir") which will allow this individual human-being to "correct" any "immoral choice" or conversely "reinforce any moral choice" – so as to "steer" that individual human-being (as well as the whole of Humanity) towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! Therefore, when the UCP computes for each consecutive UF's frame/s every exhaustive spatial pixel associated with each individual human-beings, the new discovery made by "G-D's Physics" is that this UCP's THCD's (extremely rapid, i.e., $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50!$) computation (e.g., and in particular its "Consistency" and corresponding "Goodwill/Dynamic Equilibrium Moral Principle" ("דסח") – comprises two "successive phases" (unfathomable rapid and complex) computational sequence:

a) The UCP's computation of the nine (initial) HCD's stemming from the UCP's initial "Wisdom/Free-Will" ("המכח") which materialize this UCP's (first) "Wisdom/Free-Will" ("המכח") (and more generally the UCP's initial HCD's TKI-HCDs: "Wisdom/Free-Will", "Computation" and "Consistency") – that are being "fulfilled" or "materialized" within the Ninth "Actual Computed Object" (M/T) physical features ("דסח" essentially computing these two ("more constrictive") physical features of "mass" and "time", related to every exhaustive spatial pixel's object's two "Object-consistent" ("mass") or "Object-inconsistent" ("time") physical features!

b) Following the UCP's initial (Ninth HCD's) "Actual Computed Object" (M/T) physical features (for every exhaustive spatial pixel/object in the universe), the UCP's "Infinite Wisdom" (represented by the Infinity sign) Itself – is required in order to compute the two ("more expansive") Physical Features of "space" (e.g., "Air") and "energy" ("Fire"), since these two ("more expansive") Physical Features also involve the UCP "infinitely complex" computation of the abovementioned "Dynamic Equilibrium Moral Principle" and associated selection by the UCP of one of multiple possible future/s for every Individual human-being (on the planet) in terms of its "pairing" with other (particular) human-beings towards which this (specific) Individual human-being has chosen a particular "moral/immoral choice" – which therefore necessitates the UCP's "infinitely complex" selection of a specific "future" (e.g., next subsequent UF's frame!) that would allow (for instance) a particular Individual human that has ("G-D" forbid) inflicted "pain/suffering" upon another particular human-being to experience the same (degree of) "pain/suffering" that the first Individual human-being has experienced, which would inevitably lead him/her to undertake a conscious "Teshuva" (one of those THCD's, e.g., feel a sincere "remorse" for his/her "immoral action" and also make a conscious choice to not repeat any such "immoral action", in the future!) We therefore realize that in order to compute all such possible "moral-pairs" of those Individual human-beings that have "inflicted pain" upon another "individual human-being" (at any past instance/s) and compute for them the precise (same) situation in which the "inflicting pain" individual human-being will have to experience the same ("negative/immoral") situation (in order to undertake a sincere "Teshuva") no doubt requires the UCP's Infinite Wisdom (Itself), e.g., represented through the THCD-UCF's representation of the Tenth "Universal Computational Formula" ("הכולמ") which computes the four basic physical features (of the already computed "mass"/"time" physical features in the previous ninth HCD Object Computed – coupled with the two other "space" and "energy" HCD's)!

Indeed, beyond the realization of the "infinitely complex" computation carried out by the UCP, i.e., at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50!$ (sec') which comprises these infinitely complex and ("temporally-minute") computations of the UCP through its THCD's Dimensions – divided into the two above "successive phases", for every exhaustive spatial pixel's object in the universe (simultaneously), we may begin appreciating not only the UCP's "Infinite Wisdom" and "All-Goodness" characteristics implied by its capacity to compute for each individual human-being the precise situation/s it has to experience (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) in order to "correct" and "teach" each such individual human-being the "moral lesson/s" necessary to "steer" him/her – and in fact the whole of Humanity towards the UCP's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! In fact, this profound (new) realization of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm wherein nothing in the (whole) universe occurs "accidentally", or as being "caused" by ("accidental": direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s (between either relativistic "massive objects" and their assumed "curvature of Space-Time"; or between subatomic "probe" and "target's assumed probability wave-function" etc.) – but is rather being computed specifically by this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP or "Universal Consciousness Reality", UCR) through "Personal Providence", i.e., the UCR's "All-Goodness" "intricate care" for each individual human-being (and in fact for all animals and plants as well!) in order to "steer" the whole of Humanity and the world towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! We also come to appreciate Maimonides' (and closely related Chassidic Thought) deep understanding of those Four Elements – truly representing the UCP's continuous computation of the four basic Physical Features (for every exhaustive spatial pixel's object in the universe) based on its ("minute-temporal") "successive computation": initially of the two ("more constrictive") "mass" ("Earth") & "time" ("Water") (e.g., by the first nine HCD's) and subsequently "conjoined" with the other two ("more expansive") HCD's of "space" ("Air") and "energy" ("Fire")!

Dedication

This article is dedicated to Maimonides (wjose birthdate transpired a few days ago on ו' חסין ד"י) who discovered the existence of That Singular Higher Power ("G-D") who creates all beings, planets etc.; and who also pointed at the fact that this Singular Higher Reality is steering the whole universe towards its Ultimate Perfected Geulah State in which Humanity will recognize its sole and singular Existence and live according to its Profound Characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"! It is also dedicated to the Great Lubavitcher Rabbi who guided the whole of Humanity to "open" our eyes and "See" that this "Perfected Geulah State" is already present in the world – and that Humanity (in general) has to abide and observe the "Seven Noahide Laws" (which are closely related to this Perfected Geulah State)! This article is also dedicated to the Father of the Lubavitcher Rabbi, Rabbi Levi Yitzchak Schneershan on his birth- date: חסין ד"י!

References

1. Bentwich, J. (2012a) "Harmonizing Quantum Mechanics and Relativity Theory". Theoretical Concepts of Quantum Mechanics, Intech (ISBN 979-953-307-377-3), Chapter 22: 515-550.
2. Bentwich, J. (2012b) "Theoretical Validation of the Computational Unified Field Theory". Theoretical Concepts of Quantum Mechanics, (ISBN 979-953-307-3773), Chapter 23: 551-598.
3. Bentwich, J. (2013b). "The Theoretical Ramifications of the Computational Unified Field Theory". Advances in Quantum Mechanics (ISBN 978-953-51-1089-7), Chapter 28: 671-882.
4. Bentwich, J. (2013c). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT): A Candidate Theory of Everything. Advances in Quantum Mechanics (ISBN 978-953-51-1089-7) Chapter 18: 395-436.
5. Bentwich, J. (2015). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT): A Candidate 'Theory of Everything'. Selected Topics in Application of Quantum Mechanics (ISBN 978-953-51-2126-8) Chapter 6.
6. Bentwich, J. (2014) What if Einstein was Right? Amazon Kindle Book Store.
7. Bentwich, J. (2015). On the Geometry of Space, Time, Energy, and Mass: Empirical Validation of the Computational Unified Field Theory. Unified Field Mechanics: Natural Science Beyond the Veil of Spacetime (Proceedings of VIGIER IX Conference, Morgan State University, USA, 16-19 November 2014).
8. Bentwich, J. (2016) The 'Computational Unified Field Theory': A Paradigmatic Shift. Research & Reviews: Journal of Pure & Applied Physics.
9. Bentwich, J. (2017a) The Computational Unified Field Theory: Could 'Dark Matter' & 'Dark Energy' be "Superfluous"? SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
10. Bentwich, J. (2017b) The Computational Unified Field Theory: Explaining the Universe from "Without". SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
11. Bentwich, J. (2017c). The Computational Unified Field Theory: A New 'A-Causal Computation' Physics. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
12. Bentwich, J. (2017d). The 'Computational Unified Field Theory' (CUFT) May Challenge the 'Big-Bang Theory'. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
13. Bentwich, J. (2017e). Can the 'Computational Unified Field Theory' (CUFT) Challenge the Basic Laws of Conservation? SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
14. Bentwich, J. (2017f). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT): Time "Reversal" May be Possible. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
15. Bentwich, J. (2017g). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) Transcends Relativity's Speed of Light Constraint. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics, Special Issue.
16. Bentwich, J. (2017h). The Computational Unified Field Theory's New Physics: Transcending Space, Time and Causality. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
17. Bentwich, J. (2017i). A "Supra-Spatial-Temporal Universal Consciousness Reality". Research & Reviews: Journal of Pure & Applied Physics, Special Issue: The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT)- A Paradigmatic Shift in 21st Century Physics.
18. Bentwich, J. (2017j). A New Science: An Infinite Omniscient Dynamic-Equilibrium Universal Consciousness Reality. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
19. Bentwich, J. (2017k). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) Challenges Darwin's 'Natural Selection Principle'! SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
20. Bentwich, J. (2017l). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) Challenges the Second Law of Thermodynamics. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
21. Bentwich, J. (2017m). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT): An Empirical & Mathematical Validation of the 'Computational Unified Field Theory'; SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
22. Bentwich, J. (2017n). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) New Science; SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
23. Bentwich, J. (2018a). Review: The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) New Universe: The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
24. Bentwich, J. (2018b). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT): What is "Time"? The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
25. Bentwich, J. (2018c). The Universal Consciousness Reality's Camouflage: The Physical Universe! The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
26. Bentwich, J. (2018d). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) Epilogue: Can Human Consciousness Affect the Cosmos? The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
27. Bentwich, J. (2018e). Testing the Computational Unified Field Theory's (CUFT) Differential-Critical Predictions: The Higgs-Boson Particle May Not Exist Continuously! The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
28. Bentwich, J. (2018f). The Double-Faceted Universal Consciousness Reality: A Theoretical Review. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
29. Bentwich, J. (2018g). Letter to the Editor: Dark Matter May Not Exist. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
30. Bentwich, J. (2018h). The Computational Unified Field Theory's (CUFT) Epilogue: Possible Reversal of the Arrow of Time and Abolishment of Death. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
31. Bentwich, J. (2019a). The Computational Unified Field Theory's (CUFT) New Universe. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 19 (6), Special Issue.
32. Bentwich, J. (2019b). The Computational Unified Field Theory's (CUFT) Goes Beyond the 'Standard Model': "G-d's Physics"! The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
33. Bentwich, J. (2019c). A Call for Cosmologists & Experimental Physicists: Empirical Validation of the 'Computational Unified Field Theory' (CUFT) New Paradigm through "Time-Sensitive" Astronomical and Subatomic Measurements. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 19 (6), Special Issue.
34. Bentwich, J. (2019d). The 'Computational Unified Field Theory' (CUFT): Redefining Mass, Gravity & the Physical Universe. The Glo-

- bal Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 19 (6), Special Issue.
35. Bentwich, J. (2019d). Astronomical Validation of the Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) "Critical Prediction" & Resolution of the "Universe's Accelerated Expansion Rate Enigma" (UAERE). The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 19 (6), Special Issue.
 36. Bentwich, J. (2019e) Urgent Call for Empirical Validation of the Computational Unified Field Theory's (CUFT) New 21st Century 'A-Causal Computation' (ACC) Paradigm. Acta Scientific Applied Physics, Volume 1(1).
 37. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2020a). 'G-d's Physics' (CUFT) New "Atom" & Purposeful Universe! Advances in Theoretical & Computational Physics. Volume 3 (2), p. 50-58.
 38. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2020b). An Urgent Need for "G-d's Physics" New 21st Century Paradigm's Empirical Validation. Advances in Theoretical & Computational Physics. Volume 3 (2), p. 59-65.
 39. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021). "G-d's Physics: A New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century. iUniverse. ISBN 9781532090370.
 40. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021a). "G-d's Physics" New 21st Century Paradigm: From "Law" to "Mercy"! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 41. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021b). "G-d's Physics": From Arbitrary Physical & Biological "Evolution" Towards A Universal Consciousness Reality's (UCR) Directed Morally-Perfect ("Geulah h ") Universe! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 42. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021c). "G-d's Physics": On the True Nature of "Dark-Energy" & "Dark-Matter". In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 43. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021d). The New "G-d's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Paradigm: A Morally Perfected ("Geulah h ") Directed New Physical Universe! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 44. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021e). "G-d's Physics": It's "Time" for "Geulah h"! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 45. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021f). "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) New Physics Paradigm: "Miracles" Can Happen!? In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 46. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021g). "G-d's Physics" New 21st Century Paradigm: A Complete Integration of "Space" & "Energy", "Mass" & "Time"! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 47. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021h). "G-d's Physics": Complete Unification of the Four Basic Forces of Nature & "Geulah h"! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 48. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021i). Fulfilling Einstein's Quest: "G-d's Physics" New Twenty-First Century's Paradigm's Multi-Level Computational Universe. In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 49. Dahia, F; Lemos, A.S. (2016). "Is the proton radius puzzle evidence of extra dimensions?". European Physical Journal. 76 (8): 435. arXiv:1509.08735. Bibcode:2016EPJC...76..435D. doi:10.1140/epjc/s10052-016-4266-7. S2CID 118672005
 50. Karr, J; Hilico, L. (2012). "Why three-body physics does not solve the proton-radius puzzle". Physical Review Letters. 109 (10): 103401. arXiv:1205.0633. Bibcode:2012PhRvL.109j3401K. doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.109.103401. PMID 23005286. S2CID 12752418
 51. Kuhn, Thomas S. (1962). The Structure of Scientific Revolutions (1st ed.). University of Chicago Press. pp. 172. LCCN 62019621
 52. Lestone, J.P. (4 October 2017). Muonic atom Lamb shift via simple means (Report). Los Alamos Report. Los Alamos National Laboratory. LA-UR-17-29148.
 53. Liu Y, McKeen D, Miller GA (2016). "Electrophobic Scalar Boson and Muonic Puzzles". Physical Review Letters. 117 (10): 101801. arXiv:1605.04612. Bibcode:2016PhRvL.117j1801L. doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.117.101801. PMID 27636468. S2CID 20961
 54. Onofrio, R. (2013). "Proton radius puzzle and quantum gravity at the Fermi scale". EPL. 104 (2): 20002. arXiv:1312.3469. Bibcode:2013EL...10420002O. doi:10.1209/0295-5075/104/20002. S2CID 119243594
 55. Pohl R, Antognini A, Nez F, Amaro FD, Biraben F, et al. (July 2010). "The size of the proton" (PDF). Nature. 466 (7303): 213–216. Bibcode:2010Natur.466..213P. doi:10.1038/nature09250. PMID 20613837. S2CID 4424731.
 56. Pohl R, et al. (2016a). "Laser spectroscopy of muonic deuterium". Science. 353 (6300): 669–673. Bibcode:2016Sci...353..669P. doi:10.1126/science.aaf2468. hdl:10316/80061. PMID 27516595. S2CID 206647315.
 57. Pohl R, et al. (16 September 2016b) "Proton-radius puzzle deepens". CERN Courier. After our first study came out in 2010, I was afraid some veteran physicist would get in touch with us and point out our great blunder. But the years have passed, and so far nothing of the kind has happened.
 58. Zyga, Lisa (November 26, 2013). "Proton radius puzzle may be solved by quantum gravity". Phys.org. Retrieved September 2, 2016.

Cite this article: Jehonathan Bentovish (Bentwich) (2023) G-D's Physics Novel Conception of the Four Basic Physical Features: Maimonides' & Chassidic "Four Elements"! Research & Reviews Journal of Modern Physics. **"G-D'S PHYSICS" NEW TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY SCIENTIFIC PARADIGM Special Issue:** 131-142.

Copyright: ©2023 Jehonathan Bentovish (Bentwich). This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.